

SEMI QUANTITATIVE ANALYZE WITH X-RAY FLUORESCENCE (XRF)

**Deliverable 3.3, SOPs for all Physicochemical Methods,
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Björn Stolpe	2020-01-10		FU060E	2020-05-27
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1 SUMMARY

The method can be used to analyze sample types for which no calibration is available. 70 elements can be determined semi quantitatively ($\pm 50\%$ precision) using X-ray fluorescence (XRF) and a data evaluation software program – Omnian.

The following element can be determined:

Ag, Al, Am, As, Au, Ba, Bi, Br, Ca, Cd, Ce, Cl, Co, Cr, Cs, Cu, Dy, Er, Eu, F, Fe, Ga, Gd, Ge, Hf, Hg, Ho, I, In, Ir, K, La, Lu, Mg, Mn, Mo, Na, Nb, Nd, Ni, Os, P, Pb, Pd, Pr, Pt, Pu, Rb, Re, Rh, Ru, S, Sb, Sc, Se, Si, Sm, Sn, Sr, Ta, Tb, Te, Th, Ti, Tl, Tm, U, V, W, Y, Yb, Zn, Zr.

Li, Be, B, C and N cannot be analyzed.

Omnian can sometimes falsely report elements at low concentrations (<0,1 %). Therefore, a qualitative measurement (scan) is usually performed prior to the semi quantitative analysis, to identify the elements that occur in detectable levels in the sample.

The most common sample preparation method for dry samples is to mix 5 g of sample with 0,5 g of binding wax and press the mixture to a briquette. Other sample preparation methods include the analysis of dry samples between two polymer films (sandwich), fusion of a lithium borate glass disk, direct analysis of loose powders or liquids in helium atmosphere, and direct analysis of filter paper or pieces of metal.

If the amount of sample available is very limited, the major components of the sample can be determined qualitatively using the briquette preparation method with smaller amounts of sample, e.g. 1 mg.

For light elements, such as Na, Mg, Al and Si, the X-rays can only emerge from the very surface of the sample. In order to obtain concentrations that are representative for composition of the entire sample, it is therefore important that the sample is homogeneous and finely ground.

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2 GENERAL INFORMATION

In previous versions of instruction FU060, a different data evaluation software (Uniquant) was used. Previous versions of FU060 can be found in LIMS under Method Manager.

3 HAZARDS AND SAFETY

Be careful when handling unknown samples. A risk assessment must always be performed before handling new sample types, especially if the sample may contain toxic or cancerogenic components.

Use safety goggles, protective gloves and general laboratory clothing. Be aware that unknown samples may contain toxic components.

Use shoes with steel cap when handling the pressing equipment, since it is heavy and made of massive steel.

4 QUALITY ASSURANCE OF ANALYTICAL METHOD

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5 APPARATUS

- 5.1 X-ray spectrometer (Zetium, Malvern Panalytical)
- 5.2 Steel rings for pellet preparation:
 - outside diameter 40mm, inside diameter 35mm
 - outside diameter 51mm, inside diameter 35mm
 - Polyethylene sample cups (Chemplex, CAT.NO.:1540)
- 5.3 X-ray films (Chemplex)
 - Mylar 3,6 µm
 - Mylar 6 µm
 - Polypropylene 6 µm
 - Polypropylene 12 µm
 - Prolene 4 µm

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- Microporous Film

5.4 Manual hydraulic pressing equipment

6 CHEMICALS

Binding wax - Ultra Wax, I.D. 34445, 34446

7 PROCEEDURE

7.1 Summary of the semi quantitative analysis:

- Sample preparation: e.g., briquette, sandwich, glass disk or sample cup for liquid sample
- XRF analysis: Use Omnian to analyze the sample and evaluate the results semi quantitatively and/or qualitatively
- Reporting: import data for detected elements to LIMS, add text describing the sample preparation and report results.

7.2 Sample pre-treatment:

The sample must be dry and free from volatile substances. An accurate determination of light elements requires the sample to be finely ground. Therefore, the sample is usually ground in a mortar or grinder, dried in a heating cabinet at 105°C, and allowed to cool in an exicator. The risk of sample contamination from the mortar or the grinder should be considered, especially for hard samples.

For samples deposited on a filter or other substrate, a blank filter/substrate must always be measured along with the sample.

7.3 Sample preparation

7.3.1 Pressed Briquette:

The sample should be ground as finely as possible before preparation.

The optimum sample amount is ~5g. Weigh the sample in a resealable plastic container, add 0,5g of *Ultra Wax*, close the container and mix well by shaking.

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Assemble the pressing tool as shown in the additional instruction, section 10.2. Remember to apply the steel ring (O.D. 51 mm, I.D 35 mm) inside component #3 before inserting component #4. Fill the sample in component #4 slowly introduce component #5. Avoid dust.

Position the pressing tool in the associated cabinet (if necessary, lift the piston by turning the upper screw anti-clockwise). Close the door of the cabinet. Turn the screw at the right side of the cabinet (labeled “rotate to release”) clockwise until stop. Turn the upper screw clockwise to lower the piston until it is in contact with the pressing tool (component #5). When everything is in place, press the briquette by turning the arm of the pressing instrument back and forth until reaching a pressure of approximately 10 tons. Wait for 30 seconds before releasing the pressure by turning the screw at the right side of the pressing instrument anti-clockwise.

Remove the pressing tool from the cabinet (remember to use shoes with steel cap).

Keep the piston (component #5) in place and turn the whole pressing tool upside down on a piece of paper. Component #1 will now be lifted over the rest of the pressing tool, and the steel ring with the pressed sample can be removed.

Never touch the analysis side of the briquette (the side that is aligned with the steel ring). On the other side of the briquette, use a light brush to remove dust and any loose powder that might otherwise fall into the analysis chamber of the XRF instrument.

7.3.2 Lithium borate glass disk:

Prepare the lithium borate glass disk as described in instructions FU169.

Pay special regard to the following sample types:

- Samples containing organic matter should not be fused directly, due to the risk of ignition during fusion. The organic matter can be removed prior to fusion by combustion in oven, or in some cases by drying in heating cabinet at high temperature. Pay regard to the loss of weight during combustion/drying.

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- Volatile substances will be lost during the fusion. If the sample may contain volatile substances that can be of interest for the customer, use an alternative sample preparation method.
- Samples containing high concentrations of elements that needs to be analyzed at low concentrations in other samples should be avoided, due to the risk of contamination of the platinum crucibles.

7.3.3 Direct analysis of loose powder:

The method is less reliable and accurate than the pressed briquette method but is generally non-destructive and can therefore be used for precious samples, when the sample is needed for later analysis with other methods, or when the customer wants to have the sample back.

The sample should be finely ground. The optimal sample amount is ~5 g. Weigh the sample and place it in a Chemplex-1540 sample cup. The end of the cell analyzed by XRF should be covered with a 6 µm thickness Mylar film, and the other end is covered with Microporous film. Both films are attached using associated "snap-on rings".

Ensure that none of the two films are broken or scratched. Be aware that the films can be sensitive to certain types of samples (e.g. dried chlorate) causing the films to become brittle. If there is a suspicion that the film might be affected by the sample, place the sample in heating cabinet at 60°C for 1 hour. If the films are unaffected, make a new sample that can be analyzed by XRF.

Never re-measure a sample cup, due to the risk of films breaking after repeated X-ray exposure. If a sample needs to be re-analyzed, prepare a new sample-cup.

7.3.4 Sandwich

The method is only qualitative, giving information about the major elements present in the sample. It is suitable for dry samples available in too small amounts to be analyzed semi quantitatively. If there is more than 5 g of sample available, the "loose powder" method is more reliable.

Finely ground powder is the most suitable sample type. Thin materials such as filter paper or metal foil can also be analyzed.

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Weigh the sample. Clamp the sample between two polymer films on the top of a Chemplex-1540 sample cup. 6 µm thickness Mylar film is typically used, but if there is any suspicion that the film might break, use a 12 µm thickness Polypropylene film instead. Remove dust from the sample cup using compressed air, but do not blow air directly on the films as they can be damaged or break. Tap the side of the sample cup to distribute the powdered sample evenly over the film. Ensure that no powder can escape from the sample.

Be aware that the films can be sensitive to certain types of samples (e.g. dried chlorate) causing the films to become brittle. If there is a suspicion that the film might be affected by the sample, place the sample in heating cabinet at 60°C for 1 hour. If the films are unaffected, make a new sample that can be analyzed by XRF.

Never re-measure a sandwich, due to the risk of films breaking after repeated X-ray exposure. If a sample needs to be re-analyzed, make prepare a new sandwich.

7.4 Semi quantitative analysis

Semi quantitative analysis gives a rough estimation about the concentrations of elements in a sample, with a precision within ±50 %. Omnian can measure samples either in vacuum or in helium atmosphere. However, due to the risk for dust formation and contamination of the XRF instrument, helium atmosphere is recommended for all sample types except glass disks.

7.4.1 Performing an Omnian analysis in SuperQ

7.4.2 In SuperQ, select "Measure" and choose the application "Omnian 10min He" (or Omnian 10 min for vacuum). Name the sample by the sample identity, followed by information about the sample preparation, for example:

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- B1xxxxxxx, Pressed 5g sample, 0,5g wax,
- B1xxxxxxx, Glass disk 0,8g sample

7.4.3 Evaluation of the spectra in Omnian:

- Start the Spectra application from the SuperQ window.

- Click the "open" icon , (or use CTRL+O , or select File -> Select Current measurement to analyze)
- Select the application that was used, to find the right analysis.
- Double click the file to open
- Select "Analyze" in the upper part of the window, and choose "Quantify"

A dialog box showing un-processed results will now appear on the screen. By providing the software with more information about the sample, the results given will become more accurate.

- In the bottom of the dialog box, click "Sample".
- Start at the top. Under "Sample Type", select the sample preparation method. For *Loose Powder* or *Solid*, no parameters need to be filled in. However, for *Pressed Powder* (briquette) or *Fused Bead* (glass disk), the flux/wax type and amount must be provided to calculate for the dilution of the sample.
- Check the "Apply Medium Correction" box and select "He Omnian" if the sample was analyzed in He atmosphere. If vacuum was used, leave the box empty.
- Check the "Apply Film Correction" box if a polymer film was used and select the type of film in the list.
- Always check the "Apply Drift Correction" box and select "Drift Omnian".

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- Always check the "Apply Line Overlap Correction" box.
- Click "OK"
- Go back to the result dialog box, click "Reset" and thereafter "Quantify".

Click the Printer icon to print the results.

7.1 Qualitative analysis

Qualitative analysis can give information about the major element constituents of a sample, only reporting if an element has been detected or not (YES/NO). Qualitative analysis can be used for samples that do not fulfil the criteria for semi quantitative analysis, for example when a sample is available in too small amounts, when it cannot be finely ground or when it is deposited on a filter.

A qualitative analysis (scan) is often performed prior to semi quantitative analysis, to assess the composition of the sample and avoid falsely reported elements. When the sample composition is already known, the qualitative scan can be excluded.

7.1.1 Performing qualitative analysis in Omnian

See section 7.4.1 - 7.4.3.

7.1.2 Evaluation of qualitative data with Omnian/Spectra:

- Start Spectra from the SuperQ window

- Click the "open" icon (or select File -> Select Current measurement to analyze)
- Choose the application that was used.
- Double click on the file to open it.

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A peak search is automatically performed in the spectrum. For manual peak search, select:

Click “*Graphics*” and choose “*Compare measurements graphically*”. Click “*select new measurement*” and choose reference based on preparation method. For example, if the sample was sandwiched between two films, choose the right type of film for reference. Click OK.

Compare the spectrum of the sample with the spectrum of the reference to distinguish the elements occurring in the sample but not in the reference.

8 CALCULATING AND REPORTING

Concentrations above 10 % are reported with two significant figures, while concentrations below 10 % with one significant figure only.

In LIMS, under “Comments”, provide the following information:

- A description of how the sample was prepared.
- The following text: “*XRF-UQ indicates the sample is analyzed with Omnian , SEMI- QUANTITATIVE, X-Ray fluorescence determining 70 elements. H Li Be B C N and O are not determined. Estimated concentrations are reported with one digit.*”
- If some elements are reported as below the report limit, provide the following text: “*The elements in the report detected below lower limit, "<", have been qualitatively detected in a scan*”.

9 WASTE DISPOSAL

Samples are either sent for destruction (see instruction SHM019), returned to the customer or disposed in the waste (dry samples) or sink (liquids) depending on the hazard and amount of sample. For samples without MSDS, the hazard must be judged from the element composition given by XRF. Samples sandwiched between films can usually be disposed due to the small amount.

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10 ADDITIONAL INSTRUCTIONS

10.1 Samples disposed on a filter in small amounts:

The instruction relates to samples in very low amounts (mg levels) disposed on all types of filters.

10.1.1 Pre-treatment:

If wet, the filter is first dried. Estimate the diameter of the filter area that is coated with sample (often 35 mm). Cut out a slightly smaller piece (e.g., 30 mm) of the sample-coated filter and sandwich it between two polymer films. Analyze the sandwich as described in section 7.3.4. Remember to analyze a blank filter as reference.

10.1.2 Reporting

Only use qualitative reporting, i.e., if elements are detected or not (YES/NO).

10.2 Assembling of the pressing tool:

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11 REFERENCES

- 11.1 Analytical instruction referring to Omnian:
- FU035 – Silikater mm i fast och flytande form med XRF
 - KLT020 - Halvkvantitativ analys av föroreningar i filter- och cellboxslam
 - VP052 – S, Cl, Fe och andra föroreningar i EAK